

Broadband Technique Analysis for Insulation Fault Detection and Condition Monitoring in Rotating Electrical Machines

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Abstract—This paper provides a comprehensive discussion and review of cutting-edge techniques for insulation diagnosis and monitoring in rotating electrical machines, using broadband electrical excitation. These techniques cover a frequency range from a few kHz to the MHz band and are classified into three categories. Firstly, the paper explores the application of Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) to rotating machines. Secondly, techniques based on parasitic capacitance and Common-mode (CM) broadband impedance tracking are discussed. Finally, the paper examines methodologies related to high-frequency oscillations in the phase current following a switching event.

Index Terms—insulation, condition monitoring, predictive maintenance, ac machines

I. INTRODUCTION

The reliability of rotating electrical machines represents a key aspect in several industries, where machine failures lead to catastrophic repairs and downtime economic costs. The different faults that occur in traditional industrial rotating machinery are of diverse nature. These can be related to the rotor, stator, bearings, load, etc. Industrial surveys point out that the major causes of failure are related to the stator winding and the bearings with a possibility of failure of 26% and 44% respectively [1]. With the utilization of modern Variable Frequency Drives (VFDs), the percentage of stator winding faults is expected to be higher for many applications.

The insulation of the different windings of the machine (i.e., generally stator, but also windings allocated in the rotor) represents one of the weakest constructive elements. These are normally formed by materials with adequate dielectric properties such as polymers and some minerals (e.g., epoxy resins, mica, polyesters, etc.). Several insulation degradation mechanisms take place depending on the rotating machine operating context, such as thermal and electrical ageing [2]. The degradation of the insulation may lead to the short-circuit fault of different elements of the winding (e.g., inter-turn, ground,

phase-to-phase, etc.). These short-circuits generally trigger the partial or total rewinding, and the outage of the machine. Thus, the close monitoring of insulation systems represents a key feature for predictive maintenance implementation.

Traditionally, the status of the different insulation elements is determined off-line. Standardized techniques such as the surge test, the polarization index test and off-line Partial Discharges (PD) tests have the ability to diagnose the status of several insulation elements [2], [3]. These present obvious drawbacks related to the need of machine disconnection, disassembly and the non-continuous nature of these tests. According to Stone et al. [2], several on-line insulation monitoring methodologies are commercially available. The most widespread technique is the on-line PD monitoring, which is successfully applied to a large amount of machines rated 6kV and above in the last 20 years [4]. It consists of detecting the high-frequency signals caused by a discharges located around insulation elements to diagnose the status of the insulation. This is achieved by utilizing different types of sensors such as radio-frequency antennae embedded within the winding or capacitively coupled sensors in the winding terminals. The main issue of on-line PD is the separation of the discharge pulses and the high-frequency spectra induced by the utilization of VFDs [5]. The adoption of wide band-gap semiconductors with increased voltage gradient (dv/dt) and switching frequencies represents the most critical limitation of on-line PD future development [6].

Lee et al. [7] presented a methodology based on leakage current tracking at mains frequency, which allows to estimate the value of the insulation equivalent resistance, capacitance and dissipation factor. This requires the utilization of high-sensitivity current transformers that enclose the machine single phases and the neutral point. According to Stone et al. [2] the methodology is not yet widespread for the continuous

monitoring and only devoted to periodic testing. In addition, it requires the winding to be wye-connected and the neutral point to be accessed. However, it represents a close alternative to the on-line PD method.

Several comprehensive studies and surveys were previously developed to identify challenges and research opportunities in the field. Inter-turn fault detection is recognized as one of the main research gaps for both low-voltage and medium-voltage machines [3], [8]. This was recently confirmed by the study of Lee et al. [6]. This work also highlights the lack of methods dealing with the monitoring under VFD operation and the non-invasive detection of rotor field winding insulation failures. The application of methodologies exploiting the broadband excitation of the machine windings provides new solutions to these challenges. The broadband excitation is related to frequencies ranging from the kHz until the MHz band, which cover the spectrum above the machine operating range (i.e., hundreds of Hz). The present study is aimed to the detailed analysis and review of monitoring and diagnosis techniques that utilize broadband frequency excitation. Section II describes in detail the response and representation of windings under high-frequency excitation. Section III describes the research progress on the application of Frequency Response Analysis (FRA) to rotating machines. Section IV discusses techniques based on parasitic capacitance and Common-mode (CM) broadband impedance analysis. Section V studies methodologies related to the high-frequency transient current analysis. Finally, conclusions and future work are discussed in Section VI.

II. BROADBAND FREQUENCY REPRESENTATION AND DESCRIPTION OF WINDINGS

The electromagnetic coils can be physically described in detail by utilizing multi-conductor transmission line theory [9]. The single conductors within the machine slots and forming the end-winding are represented by lumped-pi equivalent circuits by assuming that the conductors are electrically short [10]. These circuits are described by per unit length parameters (i.e., series resistance and inductance, and shunt capacitance and conductance). Different physical representations are described in [11], [12]. Figure 1 shows the lumped-pi equivalent circuit of a coil with n slot conductors and m end-winding conductors. Each parameter of the equivalent circuit symbolizes different electromagnetic phenomena. The series resistance and inductance represents the losses and magnetic flux linkage of the conductors respectively. These parameters are frequency dependent because of the skin and proximity effects, and the limited flux penetration due to the reduced penetration depth at high-frequencies. Moreover, high-frequency eddy-currents flowing within single laminations cause a shielding effect of the main flux within the slots, which dramatically affects the series inductance and resistance [13]. The mutual resistance and inductance represent the losses and flux linkage induced by the current flowing within neighbouring conductors [10]. The shunt capacitance and conductance represent the storage of electric field, and

Fig. 1. Lumped-pi per-conductor equivalent circuit of a coil with slot and end-winding sections

current conduction and the dielectric losses of the groundwall insulation respectively. The mutual capacitance and conductance represent these same phenomena in the inter-turn and phase-to-phase insulation elements. The different works found in literature for machine winding modelling consider capacitances as frequency independent even if the dielectric material permittivity varies with frequency [14]. Note that depending on the conductor section (i.e., slot or end-winding) the parameters adopt very different values since the boundary conditions for electric and magnetic field distribution dramatically vary [15].

The geometry, connection and material properties define the value of the per-unit length parameters that form the equivalent circuit. The addition of all these elements together defines the overall resistance to the ac current penetration, better known as impedance. The characteristic features of the broadband impedance are the amplitude at different frequencies, the location of the resonant points (i.e., frequencies at which the magnitude presents an inflection point) and the phase. For three phase rotating machines, the measurement can be performed in different modes depending on the measurement objective. Some of the most popular modes are the phase impedance, which is measured between machine phases, and the CM impedance, measured between three short-circuited phases and the stator housing. Figure 2 shows an example of broadband impedance measurement of two different modes for a low voltage Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) between 10 kHz and 10 MHz. Broadband frequency techniques for condition monitoring and fault diagnosis are based on the analysis of changes of this electrical signature over various frequency bands. Moreover, the machine impedance affects the high-frequency oscillations of the current in the machine terminals. Thus, the monitoring of such current components provides information about the machine impedance variation in an indirect manner, which is exploited by the methods presented in Section V.

Fig. 2. Phase and CM broadband impedance stator winding measurement for a 4.7 kW PMSM with concentrated winding

III. FREQUENCY RESPONSE ANALYSIS (FRA) APPLIED TO ROTATING MACHINES

The FRA applied to power transformers is a standard procedure utilized to detect mechanical movement or damages under different scenarios such as installation, relocation, condition alarms, etc. [16]. The FRA measurement is based on the transformer winding admittance or impedance mapping over a broadband frequency. The diagnosis is performed by comparing different measurements with a baseline reference. Deviations between the diagnosis and the baseline measurements indicate different faults and defects. The applicability of FRA to rotating machinery is not found in standards so far due to the lack of knowledge about several high-frequency phenomena in rotating machines. However, the method triggered some research attention over the last years since it presents many advantages for detecting a wide variety of faults by utilizing an on-site and quick test.

The most common type of FRA in rotating machines is the Sweep Frequency Response Analysis (SFRA). The measurement equipment applies a swept sinusoidal signal to the input port of the Equipment Under Test (EUT), and measures the response in the end port. Two different instruments are found in literature to obtain the electrical signature of a rotating electrical machine. The first one is known as gain-phase analyser, which is commercially available for application to the power transformer diagnosis. This apparatus injects a swept voltage signal in the input port and measures the voltage in the output port. The transfer function of the EUT is given by equation (1) and the test set-up is shown in Figure 3. The second apparatus for electrical signature measurement is known as impedance analyser, which is an auto-balancing impedance bridge that provides the impedance amplitude and phase, among other possible options (i.e., R-X, G-B, etc.). The apparatus has four terminals named as High Potential (H_p), High Current (H_c), Low Potential (L_p) and Low Current (L_c). Two of the terminals are connected to the high port and the remaining two to the low port of the EUT. Figure 4 shows an autobalancing

Fig. 3. Gain-phase analyser method for broadband impedance measurement

Fig. 4. Autobalancing bridge method for broadband impedance measurement

bridge schematic highlighting the most important parameters and equation 2 describes the impedance computation. Besides the connection schematics and the working principle, the most important difference between the two equipments lays on the voltage level of the oscillator and on their input impedance. Gain-phase analyser utilizes matched 50Ω resistances in the measurement terminals while the impedance analyser uses an undefined large input impedance.

$$Y_{dB} = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{V_{in}}{V_o} \right| \quad (1)$$

$$Z_{EUT} = \frac{V_{in}}{I_{EUT}} = R_r \frac{V_{in}}{V_o} \quad (2)$$

The research in the field is traditionally oriented to the off-line fault detection of stator windings in low- medium-voltage machines. The work of Florkowski et al. [17], [18] studies the effect of different short-short circuit faults in the off-line broadband admittance up to 6 MHz. Both phase-to-phase and inter-turn short circuits are physically implemented and simulated by using the model proposed by Grandi et al. [19]. The most interesting observation is how the inter-turn short circuit is detected by tracking the resonant frequencies in terms of shifting and damping both in the experimental test and in the simulation. Lamarre et al. [20] applied SFRA to the stator winding of different high-power machines with the aim of identifying insulation ageing indicators. The authors compare results between a gain-phase and an impedance analyser. Moreover, they highlight the importance of better understanding some high-frequency phenomena to provide further understanding of the FRA results. The presence of the rotor in rotating electrical machines represents on the the most important drawbacks for SFRA reliability. Platero

et al. [21] analyse in detail the influence of a synchronous machine rotor on the broadband admittance curves, where a fixed reference rotor position is proposed for SFRA test standardization. Sant'Ana et al. [22] extend the knowledge about the rotor position effect stating that even cylindrical rotors could cause the broadband impedance or admittance to vary. The authors propose different statistical indexes to neglect the effect of the rotor. In [23] the authors evaluate the applicability of SFRA to detect inter-turn short-circuits in form-wound windings. Several works are oriented towards the off-line SFRA detection of inter-turn, phase-to-phase or ground short-circuits in low-voltage machines by utilizing several statistical indicators [24]–[26]. In [27] the authors utilize SFRA analysis to detect field winding short-circuits in a medium power salient pole synchronous machine, while [28] studies the detection of broken rotor bars of squirrel cages and damper windings. Some studies devoted to detect insulation ageing can be found in [29] and [30]. The latter tracks the coil impedance evolution over several progressive ageing mechanisms, which is particularly interesting to link impedance curves and insulation degradation. A more recent research trend consists of the off-line SFRA diagnosis of salient pole windings for MVA-range synchronous generators. Thus, inter-turn and ground faults in large salient poles are studied in [31] and [32] respectively. In addition, [33], [34] deal with the automatic detection and assessment of such faults in large salient poles.

The on-line SFRA technique applied to rotating machines brings interesting capabilities such as continuous monitoring of the broadband electrical signature. The most utilized approach is the superposition of a high-frequency signal in the main power bus via standard equipment (i.e., impedance and gain-phase analysers). In [35] a signal generator is utilized to inject the high-frequency excitation in a low pass filtered main power cord. The response is measured by current and voltage sensors and a separated processing unit computes the impedance for each frequency. The work does not present application results that support this technology. Sant'Ana et al. propose a LC coupling that allows to link an impedance analyser to the main power cord [36]. The main drawback of this technique is the interference of the coupling impedance with the EUT. The coupling is designed to minimise the impedance overlap between coupling and motor. An active coupling technology is introduced in [37] to avoid the direct connection between measurement equipment and power cord. In this way, the impedance overlap between coupling and motor is avoided. However, the system for active cancellation presents increased complexity when compared with the passive coupling. Another example of passive coupling for on-line SFRA can be found in [38], where the authors developed small galvanically insulated RLC circuits to couple the measurement instrument and the main power cord. These circuits bring a cost-effective solution for industry in opposition to the previously described active filtering. A novel approach for on-line SFRA is presented in [39], where a vector network analyser is utilized instead of gain-phase and impedance analysers.

Moreover, the coupling between instrument and power cord is performed in a wireless manner through the utilization of inductive couplers.

IV. INSULATION MONITORING BY CM IMPEDANCE AND PARASITIC CAPACITANCE ANALYSIS

The monitoring of the broadband CM impedance and the values of diverse parasitic capacitances provides useful information about the insulation status. Werynski et al. [40] studied how the turn-to-turn parasitic capacitance variation affects the broadband impedance resonant frequencies. They proposed a rather complex on-line method to monitor the variation of the resonance point by measuring stray flux caused by an intentional signal injection at the resonant frequency. The method of Perisse et al. [41] is based on the injection of low voltage signals at different frequencies and to measure the phase current to map the resonant frequencies of the broadband impedance.

A more modern trend is based on the well-known on-line capacitance and dissipation factor technique [7]. The basic working principle of these works is depicted in Figure 5. Zhang et al. [42] propose the utilization of broadband high-sensitivity current transformers enclosing all three phases of the machine. In this way, the leakage current up to 3.5 kHz can be measured without accessing the machine neutral point. However, only the general insulation status is obtained and no phase distinction is made. In [43] the authors map the on-line CM impedance by utilizing signal injection. This method identifies with adequate sensitivity variations of the

Fig. 5. (a) On-line capacitance and dissipation factor measurement schematic with recent extensions, (b) Leakage current decomposition and insulation equivalent circuit, reconstruction from [7]

groundwall insulation but cannot track changes in the turn insulation due to the low amplitude of the injected signals. The work of Zheng et al. [44]–[47] presents the most recent extension to the on-line capacitance and dissipation factor method. All these works present similar experimental set-up for the on-line insulation monitoring, which is close to the traditional scheme of Figure 5 but also including broadband phase-to-ground voltage probes. In [44] the groundwall and the phase insulation are monitored by tracking two different parasitic capacitances, which are obtained from leakage current and phase-to-ground voltage broadband measurements. These capacitances are tracked around the switching frequency value, which do not reach the CM impedance resonant frequency, when inductance affects the impedance value. The insulation ageing is emulated by inserting additional capacitances between phases and between a phase and ground. The main contribution of [45] lays on the inter-turn insulation monitoring by tracking the variation of high-frequency CM impedance above the resonant frequency. This work is extended in [46], where the location of the insulation degradation is studied. In [47] the effect the insulation state is monitored by tracking a generic capacitance value at the switching frequency. This is performed on a PMSM generator connected to the grid via rectifier inverter system.

V. HIGH-FREQUENCY TRANSIENT CURRENT MONITORING

The impedance variation caused by insulation ageing induces an alteration in the transient current ringing when VFDs switching takes place. Figure 6 depicts the interaction between the voltage switching and the high-frequency transient current components. In addition to the broadband machine impedance, several physical phenomena influence the transient current oscillation and its spectrum. On the one hand, the mismatch between cable and motor impedance causes the voltage signals to be partially reflected back towards the inverter. If the incident voltage wave is not completely absorbed due to the impedance mismatch, the reflected wave overlaps causing an overshoot in the motor terminals. This phenomenon particularly affects motors with long cables and inverter fast rising pulses (i.e., specially critical for wide band-gap semiconductors) [48]. On the other hand, according to Ran et al. [49] the different absorbed high-frequency current components propagate in different modes within the winding, which is known as multi-modal propagation. Particularly, the CM current propagation can be divided into a high-frequency component immediately following the switching event, and a much lower frequency component. The first, flows towards ground through the parasitic capacitance of the terminal and first turns of the winding while the second penetrates the winding and leaks to ground all along its length. Figure 6 shows the multi-modal decomposition schematic for a motor fed by a rectifier-inverter system.

The method presented in [51] focuses on the measurement of phase current high-frequency transients to detect variations on the high-frequency impedance. The measured signal is processed and transformed to obtain its spectra via Fast

Fourier Transform (FFT). By comparing the healthy and faulty measurement spectra different insulation state indicators are extracted. In addition, different motorettes of form-wound coils are tested in [52], where the ability of the method to detect thermal ageing and moisture presence is tested. The methodology performs one measurement per-phase, enabling the phase discrimination of the indicator. The authors of these works highlight the impact of the sampling frequency selection on the result validity. Leuzzi et al [53] study the impact of induced electrical ageing on the high-frequency current and on the off-line broadband impedance. The ageing is artificially caused by an accelerated ageing test that impose high amplitude voltage signals in the machine terminals. Several indicators are obtained from the measured current in time and frequency domain. One of the main conclusions is that the progression of the electrical ageing shows high randomness thus, not concluding on the adequacy of the method. Xiang et al. [50] present a novel methodology based on the multi-modal current propagation principle described in Figure 6. The authors propose an insulation health indicator extracted from the low-frequency CM component of the phase current. The required sampling frequency is reduced, which represents a significant advantage. However, only the phase insulation overall status can be tracked. A similar approach is presented in [54], where the authors pursue the insulation status monitor of the first coil (or line-end coil). This is particularly important for randomly-wound low-voltage machines fed by fast rising VFDs, where the risk of PDs in the first coils dramatically increases. In this work, the different modal components of

Fig. 6. (a) Phase current high-frequency oscillation generation mechanism, reconstruction from [50], (b) multi-modal current propagation schematic

the phase current are separated by utilizing the Variational Mode Decomposition technique, which provides three different intrinsic mode functions each of them related to one of the propagation modes. The high-frequency CM component is utilized to track the variation of the line-end coil capacitance. The major drawback of this methodology is the utilization of high sensor bandwidth and high sampling frequency.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper performs the analysis and review of several rotating electrical machine insulation status diagnosis and monitoring techniques based on broadband signal excitation. The physical representation and equivalent circuit of a winding is presented, where the meaning of each parameter is discussed in depth. Then, the FRA applied to rotating machines both in the off-line and on-line mode is analysed with special emphasis on the utilized instrumentation. Following, the utilization of parasitic capacitance and CM impedance to monitor different insulation elements is explained and reviewed. Finally, the working principle and propagation of high-frequency current transients is presented and the techniques exploiting this method are analysed in depth.

Regarding FRA in rotating machines, the analysis of existing literature points out that off-line diagnosis techniques offer interesting solutions in the case of sensitive constructive parts of the machine which cannot be easily accessed (e.g., large power damper windings, salient pole windings etc.). The application of off-line SFRA for insulation fault diagnosis still requires further research and industrial expertise in order to be standardized. Regarding on-line techniques, the coupling between instrument and main power cord represents the most challenging aspects. Improvements on the noisiness of the signals and reliability of the results are required. The source of the on-line noise (i.e., rotor position variation, coupled electric noise, etc.) is still not completely identified up to date. Overall, research oriented to better understand the variations of the impedance or admittance curves under different types of faults, degradation and machine operating conditions is required. The monitor of parasitic capacitances and CM impedance presents interesting features regarding sensitivity and identification of the ageing location. The monitoring of high-frequency current transients presents an easy and straight way to obtain information. However, further research effort regarding the sensitivity and applicability of these methods is necessary in order to be widespread. Fast and efficient signal processing techniques for mode decoupling and the elimination of other components influence (e.g., cable influence on the high-frequency components) may need to be further explored. Some of the discussed techniques utilizing lumped capacitance insertion need to be tested under realistic ageing scenarios, where these may not present the same sensitivity as observed for the artificial insertion.

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